

A study of magnetic phase transition in BiFe_{0.5}Cr_{0.5}O₃ thin films deposited over Pt (111)/Ti/SiO₂/Si substrate

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Abstract

BiFe_{0.5}Cr_{0.5}O₃ (BFCO) nanostructured thin films were prepared by sol-gel method over Pt (111)/Ti/SiO₂/Si substrate. The crystal structure of BiFe_{0.5}Cr_{0.5}O₃ films has been investigated using X-ray diffraction and it reveals that the films are formed at a high crystallinity with high degree of orientation depending on the deposition conditions. Rietveld refinement for the film has been done using Jana 2006. The multiferroic character of BFCO is proven by ferroelectric and magnetic measurements showing that the films exhibit both ferroelectric and magnetic hysteresis at normal room temperature. In addition, Spin-cooling behaviors of BFCO films have investigated through temperature dependent magnetic studies from 0 K to 300 K.

Keywords: Multiferroic, refinement, spin-cooling